

Family Structure and Student Discipline in Public Boarding Secondary Schools in Western Region of Kenya

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Abstract:

Discipline in schools is an issue that especially concerns educators, parents, and other stakeholders. In an environment that lacks order and discipline, it is impossible for students to learn effectively. Thus, order and discipline are indispensable for achieving positive educational results. The family assumes a pivotal role in shaping the early years of an individual. The purpose of this research was to examine the influence of family structure on student discipline in public boarding secondary schools in Western region of Kenya. Family composition and structural-functionalism theories served as guiding principles for the research. The investigation was conducted

using an ex post facto design. The study's target population consisted of 5583 class teachers and 369 deputy principals (administrators-in-charge) from 369 public boarding secondary institutions. The sample included 123 deputy Principals and 558 class teachers from the 123 randomly selected schools. Simple random sampling was used to select 558 class teachers while purposive sampling was used to select 123 deputy Principals. For the purpose of data collection from the participants, a questionnaire and an interview schedule were employed. The assessment of the instruments' reliability was conducted using the test-retest method, results of the pilot study reveal that all scales were trustworthy because their reliability values were more than the required threshold of 0.7. Data was analyzed using frequency, percentages, weighted averages, correlations and multi-regression analysis. The study concluded that family structure influence the discipline of students in public secondary schools.

Keywords: *Discipline, Family Structure, Influence, Student.*

Introduction

The family is an essential social element in every society. It provides essential human necessities such as shelter, time for rest, clothing, sanitation,

and adequate food, as well as care, affection, tenderness, pure water, and shelter. Family structures are contingent upon the socioeconomic, environmental, and occasionally political circumstances that are prevalent at the

time. The maintenance and upbringing of children falls under the purview of the family (Vassiliki, 2013). Family structure as it pertains to the present study will encompass the following situations: intact families consisting of a father and mother; single parent families comprising only one parent; step parent families comprising two parents who are not biological parents to the children; and families consisting of adopted children. The influence of the various roles that women (mothers) and men (fathers) perform within the family on the girls and boys born or raised in the household.

The Merriam-Webster Dictionary (2018) defines the family as the fundamental social unit, which traditionally comprises two parents responsible for the upbringing of their children, or a group of people residing in close proximity and typically led by a single individual. Family structures include nuclear, extended, step/blended, single-parent, adopted, and foster families. The extent to which each family structure contributes to a child's education largely depends on that family structure (Meleen, 2019). According to an initial investigation, 11% of children originated from intact families wherein their biological parents resided, whereas 89% experienced family structure disruption (Behere, Basnet, & Campbell, 2017). The influence of family structure on individuals begins during infancy and persists through adolescence (Santiago et al., 2019).

There is evidence to suggest that children who come from cheerful homes exhibit greater emotional stability and maturity (Strans, 2008). Additionally, children hailing from positive household climates demonstrate virtuous attitudes that contribute to their academic success, favorable perceptions of school authorities, intellectual curiosity, seamless transition to the school day, and enthusiasm for extracurricular engagements. Conversely, children residing in unfavorable environments exhibit the opposite conduct. Excellent students are, in fact, the product of excellent parents (Goode 1990). Additionally, he maintained that there is a higher propensity for adolescent delinquency among offspring of employed parents compared to those of non-working

parents. Whatever the employment status of the parents, he considers inadequate child supervision to be the root cause of delinquency. As a result, parents must personally supervise a significant portion of their children rather than entrusting this laudable responsibility to inexperienced housekeepers. According to Onyehahi (2004), delinquency can be defined as a deviation from societal norms, which can be seen as a form of rebellion against established social control mechanisms that promote consistency, stability, and coherence in human behavior and way of life. A correlation exists between the level of delinquency and one's home environment. Parents serve as role models for their children, who imitate and internalize their values, regardless of whether such conduct is culturally accepted. In traditional African society, the household functions as an educational institution unto itself. Undoubtedly, it serves as the foundational element upon which the child's subsequent academic achievements emerge. The cultural demands of each household sufficiently fulfill the requirements prior to the pursuit of formal education (Fafunwa 1994). Thus, it can be inferred that the household has the ability to motivate children, either positively or negatively, via reinforcement. Regarding the impact of the household on the child, Bolarin (1992) noted that the conduct exhibited by the child at home significantly influences their conduct when they are not in the home. Undoubtedly, the research demonstrated that a child's upbringing significantly impacts their future social behavior and way of life.

The behaviour of students has been observed to be influenced by the structure of their families. Deviant behaviors and depression are more prevalent among adolescents from non-intact families, including single-parent or reconstituted families, in comparison to their counterparts from intact families. According to Andrea et al. (2016), significant mechanisms by which family structure influences deviant behavior and melancholy in adolescents are the existence of parental monitoring and school connectedness. Moreover, the impact of familial structure on the conduct of pupils is not contingent upon their gender. Additionally, the composition and

attributes of the familial unit may exert an impact on the probability of young individuals participating in sexual activity, as well as the age at which they commence such behavior. Early sexual debut is more prevalent among adolescents residing with one parent as opposed to those residing with both parents. As a result, the structure of the family has a substantial impact on the development of deviant behavior, melancholy, and sexually risky behaviors among students.

The dynamics within a family are vital to the development of adolescents. There are numerous responsibilities that a parent must fulfill in order to facilitate a seamless transition for their child into adolescence. A traditional family (i.e., married with two biological parents) is one in which both parents actively participate in the upbringing of their child. The father typically is preoccupied with the adolescent's behavior, whereas the mother assumes responsibility for the emotional aspects of the adolescent's development. The child's primary caregiver is the mother, who provides assistance with daily activities; the father, on the other hand, generally fulfills the responsibilities of earning a living and managing the household (Maurya, Parasar, & Sharman, 2015). In a longitudinal study involving 411 participants, Juby and Farrington (2001) discovered that delinquency behaviors were more prevalent among adolescents living with a single parent.

Family structure is a term used to describe the individuals who comprise a household and are related through marriage or ancestry; it is typically applied when at least one child under the age of 18 resides in the household. Modern terminology includes the terms "two-parent," "one-parent," and "living with neither parent" to refer to these arrangements (e.g., institutionalized children, adoptive families, grandparent families or other relatives, foster care families). Additional developments in family life since the mid-1940s have led to the emergence of more complex classifications for family structures, including binuclear families, multigenerational families, blended families, and single-parent plus partner families (which

include cohabiting couples of the same and opposite sexes) (Pasley & Petren, 2015).

Conversely, family structure provides insight into the condition of an intact or fractured family. Within the framework of this research, a "broken family" is defined as a unit that has undergone division or separation due to diverse factors, including parental demise, divorce, separation, or abandonment. Consequently, children may be brought up by stepparents, stepparents, or other relatives. Conversely, an intact family is characterized by the cohabitation and presence of both biological parents within the household. It is not always the case that a family's intactness indicates optimal functioning or adequate care for its children; intact families can experience a variety of normal conflicts and problems, in addition to life-threatening circumstances. The significance of family structural analysis stems from the fact that the family is the child's most influential and informal socializing agent in society; furthermore, the child's future is contingent on the family unit. It aids children in identifying and obtaining significant societal objectives. Academic performance is subtly influenced by the family environment and heritage, which can either support or hinder it.

The establishment and formation of a child's personality are significantly influenced by the entirety of the family unit. Conversely, an unfinished and shattered family, particularly in cases of parental divorce, profoundly detrimentally affects a child's character, particularly with regard to their social conduct. Youth development and constructive guidance are exclusively possible through "real homes" that consist of complete families. Particularly with regard to the development of values and conduct, the ambiance within incomplete families is detrimental to the individual. The lack of authoritative figures and exemplary conduct has an adverse effect on development and creates an unfavorable impression. The earlier in an individual's life the factors contributing to this undesirable family incompleteness manifest, the more protracted this adverse circumstance persists, the more estranged the individual

becomes, and the greater the likelihood that his or her behavior will deteriorate.

Positive progressive outcomes are more likely to develop in adolescents residing in two-parent households as opposed to those residing in single-parent households. Maurya, Parasar, and Sharman (2015) aimed to elucidate that parents have the ability to establish a rapport with their children, monitor one another's disciplinary progress, and ensure that they are jointly spending quality time with their children. The presence of two parents in a household not only contributes positively to the development of the adolescent but also ensures the generation of two incomes. Because these traditional families enjoy greater economic stability, their stressors are diminished. In the United States, two-parent households have greater access to benefits such as health insurance, higher income, and higher education than single parent households (Reczek, Spiker, Liu, & Crosnoe, 2016). Conversely, single-parent households face greater economic, social, and emotional risks. This socioeconomic disadvantage may heighten the anxiety of single parents. Single-parent households encounter greater difficulties in managing tension, which can lead to financial difficulties and strain between the parent and adolescent (Behere, Basnet, & Campbell, 2017). Single-parent households encounter the formidable obstacle of destitution. An estimated fifty percent of single-parent households are impoverished, compared to five percent of two-parent households (Behere, Basnet, & Campbell, 2017). As a result of these financial difficulties and stressors, a parent may be compelled to increase their working hours and experience social isolation. This may result in the adoption of a less involved parenting style by the parent.

Typically, adolescents are subject to less supervision when their parents withdraw. According to Amato and Patterson (2017), unsupervised adolescents exhibit diminished academic achievement. They engage in more risky behavior and are more likely to become juvenile parents than adolescents raised in two-parent households. The alterations in the family unit may disturb the equilibrium of these young individuals, leading to emotional distress triggers

that may have an impact on their developmental progress (Alami et al., 2014). Price and Kunz (2003) discovered in a meta-analysis of 72 adolescents that delinquency is more prevalent among those who are raised in divorced households.

According to research cited by Qaiser, Ishtiaq, Zaitoon, and Wahab (2012), a multitude of factors contribute to students' subpar and unsatisfactory academic performance. As per their assertions, these factors comprise parental illiteracy, domestic complications and issues, sizable family size, neglectful parental attention and control, low socioeconomic status, and family structure. In the context of this research, the term "family structure" is defined as consisting of either one or two parents. Consequently, the purpose of this study is to investigate whether or not these structures affect student conduct.

Two-Parent Family

This household comprises an intact set of parents and offspring. Michelle (2012) characterizes it as the archetypal family structure, revered by society for its perceived efficacy in child-rearing. Because both parents are present, parental participation in the children's activities, education, and growth is substantial. Simply put, children residing in two-parent households receive greater financial, social, and physical support from both parents (Fagan & Churchill, 2012). This is due to the fact that both parents have greater access to income, savings, and employment opportunities compared to single parents (Amato, 2005).

Single parents are unable to provide their children with the same amount of time, affection, and supervision as two-parent families (Peter, 2016). This is due to the fact that when parenting becomes problematic, the two parents can provide relief for one another (Peter, 2016). In addition to providing greater social and emotional support, this type of family is likely to expose children to both maternal and paternal figures, which are conducive to their healthy socio psychological development. Ella, Odok, and Ella (2015) assert that society considers the nuclear family unit, comprising two parents and

children, to be the quintessential setting for childrearing. They believe that such children benefit from the financial security of two parents, which provides them with greater opportunities and strength and stability. Moreover, these children tend to fare better on a variety of cognitive, emotional, and behavioral requirements.

Single-Parent Family

The academic performance of a pupil may be adversely affected by the nature of their family background. In support of this claim, Bengesai and Nzimande (2020) contend that the accessibility of educational resources is contingent upon the nature of the family. For example, children who are raised in single-parent households face educational disadvantages. This is due to the fact that mothers who are single parents are more likely to have limited financial resources, possess low levels of education, and may not have the time to fully engage in their children's academic pursuits (Makewa et al., 2010; Uwaifo, 2012). These views are corroborated by Amoakohene (2013), who posits that academic performance may be adversely affected by single parenthood due to the increased likelihood of single parents being impoverished and their limited availability to participate in their children's educational pursuits.

A single parent is an adult who is not married and is responsible for the majority of the daily and routine obligations associated with raising one or more children. Unintended pregnancies, particularly among adolescents, and the death or incarceration of a companion, as well as the separation or divorce of married parents, can all lead to such parenting. It may also occur due to a conscious decision. Put simply, individuals, particularly single women, frequently search for a known or anonymous sperm donor with the intention of conceiving and becoming single mothers. The demographics of single parenting indicate a global increase in the number of children residing in single parent households, as single parenting has become the norm in the United States and is a trend in a number of other nations, according to Wikipedia (2012).

Furthermore, poor academic outcomes may result from the inability of an illiterate single mother to provide academic support for her children, as cautioned by Videnovic and Lazarevic (2017). Conversely, Abuya et al. (2019) contend that children hailing from two-parent households enjoy educational benefits due to the possibility that both parents possess sufficient financial resources and leisure to devote to their children's academic pursuits. Students hailing from single-parent households exhibit subpar academic achievement as a result of parental involvement, income, and education deficiencies. Additionally, solitary parenting is detrimental to the mental, emotional, and psychological health of children. Ntumi et al. (2016) expressed concern regarding the fact that children hailing from single-parent households experience intermittent feelings of despair and emotional distress, which consequently disrupts their engagement in educational activities.

According to Oke (2015), children hailing from single-parent households may experience personality disorders, which can potentially manifest as antisocial behavior. Kimani and Kombo (2020) expressed comparable views, contending that children who are raised in households without a father experience an identity crisis and encounter disciplinary issues. The absence of one parent does not have a psychological impact on the offspring. Hamid et al. (2013) makes the observation that single mothers may encounter psychological distress as a consequence of the pressures associated with parenting their children alone, which could potentially have an impact on the social behavior of their children. Furthermore, it is frequently the case that children who are raised in households headed by a mother do not have access to a positive role model (Clowes et al., 2013). To emulate, children require a parental role model. In comparison to their classmates from two-parent households, students from single-parent households perform inadequately for the reasons outlined here. Numerous scholarly investigations have been conducted to examine the impact of familial factors on the academic achievement of students. An example of a study that examined the impact of family

structure on student academic achievement was conducted by Johnson (2015). In the study, 96 students participated. The information regarding the students was extracted from the Student Information System (SIS) of the chosen Southeast Missouri school district. Student performance was significantly higher for those with both parents, according to the findings of the study, than for those from single-parent households. However, a smaller sample size of 96 students was utilized in this research, whereas the current study comprised 498 respondents. This study was conducted in a foreign setting, whereas the present investigation was conducted domestically in Kenya. Japan has experienced a rise in the percentage of single-parent households as a consequence of divorce, similar to numerous other nations (Zhou, 2014).

As per the Ministry of Health, Labor and Welfare (2011), single-parent households tend to exhibit a higher prevalence of poverty. Academically, children from these impoverished single-parent households also tend to perform poorly. To support these findings, Tobishima (2018) examined the impact of single parenthood on the academic achievement of Japanese children using data from the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA). A statistically significant difference in academic achievement existed between pupils from two-parent households and those from single-parent households, according to the study's findings. Students from single-parent households had poor academic performance, according to the findings of the study, because their mothers had low levels of education and income. This was likely the case, given that a parent's capacity to provide educational resources is impacted by income, and a child's academic support may be influenced by their level of education. The present investigation collected secondary data, whereas this study utilized secondary data. An investigation by Azumah et al. (2018) into the impact of family structure on the academic achievement of children in Kumasi Metropolis, Ghana, revealed that no statistically significant distinction existed in terms of academic performance between children hailing from

single parent families and those from dual-parent households. Existing empirical evidence indicates that students from single-parent households are academically disadvantaged in comparison to their counterparts from dual-parent households. However, the results of this study contradict these findings. A sample of eighty individuals was selected for this investigation through the use of a stratified random sampling method and a case study design. In contrast, the present study utilized a descriptive research survey design, which distinguishes it from the aforementioned case study design. In contrast to the reviewed research, which was conducted overseas, the current study was carried out domestically.

Maposa et al. (2020) conducted a quantitative study in Kuwadzana, Harare, Zimbabwe, utilizing an ex post facto research design and a sample size of 34 students. The objective of the study was to determine the impact of single parenting on academic achievement. The findings indicated that children hailing from single-parent households exhibited comparatively lower achievement levels in comparison to their peers from dual-parent households. The findings of this study are consistent with prior research that indicates a detrimental impact of solitary parenthood on academic achievement (Amato, 2010). In contrast to the reviewed study, which utilized an ex post facto research design, the current investigation implemented a descriptive survey research design. The present study utilized inferential analysis methods to establish the relationship between variables, a feature that was entirely absent in the reviewed study with regard to data analysis. Research has been conducted in Kenya regarding the effects of single parenthood.

In light of the aforementioned, NATO (2016) investigated the impact of family structure on the scholastic achievement of secondary school pupils in the Bungoma East Sub-County of Kenya. The present investigation utilized an ex post facto research design and incorporated a sample of 323 participants who were chosen via a straightforward random sampling method. There was a faint negative correlation between

single-parent households and students' academic achievement, according to the study's findings. The results of the study provide additional evidence in favor of claims that solitary parenting negatively affects the academic performance of children. While both studies were conducted in Kenya, the former utilized an ex post facto research design, whereas the latter employed a descriptive survey research design.

Billings (2012) argues that children from such households become delinquents due to the fact that they are frequently deprived of the security, protection, and affection that ought to be provided by both parents, all of which have a negative impact on their conduct. Similarly, Stone (2012) posits that offspring of single parents are substantially more prone to manifesting negative school attitudes, malnutrition, illness, and insufficient rest, all of which can have a detrimental impact on academic performance and achievement beginning in infancy. Due to their generally lower incomes compared to two-parent families, single parent households face greater financial limitations when it comes to providing sufficient funds to support their children's educational requirements. Providing and sustaining a conducive learning environment for their children is typically a more challenging task for solitary parents, who must also manage the dual obligations of employment and childrearing (UNESCO, 2012).

In their study, Kimaru et al. (2020) examined the impact of familial structure on the scholastic achievement of secondary school pupils attending public schools in Kiambu County, Kenya. To ascertain the participating institutions, a descriptive survey research design was implemented, supplemented with a stratified random sampling technique. A simple random sampling method was utilized to select a sample of 385 students. There were no statistically significant differences observed in the academic performance of children from single parent families compared to those from both parent families, according to the study. The results of this study are in contrast with research conducted in Western nations, which suggests that students from two-parent households

exhibit superior academic achievement compared to those from single-parent households (Sun & Li, 2011; Sandstrom & Huerta, 2013; Hampden-Thompson & Galindo, 2015). Due to the need for additional research into the inconsistencies, this study was carried out in public secondary institutions located in the Western region of Kenya.

Materials and Methods

Research Design

The study utilized an ex-post-facto research design. According to Isangedighi, Asim, and Joshua (2004), this design is an empirical investigation in which the researchers have no control over the independent variables since they have already manifested or are immutable. Because the independent variable and the dependent variable as of the period of investigation have already occurred, the design is therefore best suited for this study (Oso& Onnen,2005). The researcher used this approach because family background variables, such as parenting behaviour, family income, family structure and parent's educational background had already had an influence on the student discipline and they had no control over what had already happened (Best and Kahn, 2000).

Area of Study

This study was carried out in Western region, which was reconstituted into four counties namely; Bungoma, Busia, Kakamega and Vihiga (Appendix iv) as per the new constitution of Kenya promulgated on 27th August 2010. Gay (2003) observes that the ideal setting for a research study directly satisfies the researcher's interests. Therefore, this study focused on family background and student discipline in public boarding secondary schools in Western region. The province is situated in Western part of Kenya and extends from latitudes 00 to 10N (about 125km) and longitudes 330551E to 350101E (about 140km).The total area of western province is approximately 8434 sq.kms. Rainfall in the province is relatively high with mean annual rainfall varying from 1000mm in the Eastern part to about 2000mm around

Kakamega. The driest months are December-February while heaviest rainfall occurs in April and May (Kenya National Bureau of Statistics, 2019). The primary economic pillar of the region predominantly relies on small-scale agriculture, with minimal industrial and commercial expansion. As a result, the earnings of the inhabitants have remained at the same level and this has caused the region to be one of the top five donors to the National poverty index, with a rate of 3.79 percent (Otieno, 2014). Hence, the communities in the region highly prioritize education as a crucial factor for economic progress (Murumbakiveu et al., 2017). Nevertheless, the occurrences of student uprisings and lack of discipline at public boarding schools within the region are a significant cause for concern (Wakachala, Barasa & Likoko, 2021).

Study Population

According to the Ministry of Education report (2022), Western region of Kenya comprises of 5583 class teachers and 369 Deputy Principals (in charge of administration) from 369 public boarding secondary schools.

Sampling Procedures and Sample Size

A sample is a subset of a target population that is selected to serve as a representative (Kindsiko, 2019). Proper sampling methods and the size of the sample are essential in guaranteeing that the study accurately reflects the target population. According to Beck (2013), the size of the sample is still crucial in order to achieve the required level of confidence in the results. A total of 123 public boarding secondary schools, which accounted for 30% of the population, were chosen as a sample (Mugenda & Mugenda, 2003). Purposive sampling was utilized to select a total of 123 deputy Principals (Maxwell, 2012).

A sample of 1954 class teachers, which accounted for 25% of the target population (5583 class teachers), was drawn. Mugenda & Mugenda (2003) suggest that a sample size ranging from 10% to 50% is an appropriate representation of the target population. In order to reduce any potential bias and ensure equal opportunities for all class teachers, simple random sampling method was used to select 558 class teachers (Levitt et al., 2018). The allocation of participants is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Sample Size of the Study

Participants	Target Population (N)	Sample Size (n)	Sample Proportion	Sampling Technique
Deputy Principals	369	123	33.3%	Purposive
Teachers	5583	558	10.0%	Simple Random

Source: Ministry of Education Office, 2024

Results

Family Structure on Student Discipline

The third of this study was to examine the influence of family structure on student discipline in public boarding secondary schools in Western region of Kenya.

To address this objective the class teachers were asked to give their views on whether family structure influences student discipline in public boarding secondary schools in Western region of Kenya. The family structure was categorized as follows: Two Parents, One Parent,

Reconstituted Family and living with other relatives. The results are reported in Table 2.

Data from Table 2 shows that 189(48.3%) of class teachers indicated that students who have two parents relate best with authority. 76 (5.5%) class teachers indicated that students who have one parent relate well with authority. 108 (27.7 %) class teachers indicated that students who live with other relatives relate well with authority and 72 (18.5%) class teachers indicated that students from a reconstituted families relate well with authority. This suggests that students who have two parents and students who live with other relatives relate best to authority while

students who live with one parent relate worst with authority.

Table 2. Family Structure

Students' behaviour	A. Two Patents		B. One Parent		C. Reconstituted family		D. Living with other relatives	
Relate well with authority	189	48.3%	22	5.5%	72	18.5%	108	27.7%
Obeys rules	171	44.0%	33	8.1%	75	19.1%	113	28.8%
Uncooperative and unruly	27	6.9%	78	20.0%	176	45.1%	110	28.0%
Influences peers negatively	54	13.9%	86	21.9%	97	24.8%	154	39.4%
Relate poorly with colleagues	111	28.5%	153	39.1%	71	18.2%	56	14.2%

Table 2 also shows that class teachers indicated that students who have two parents obey rules the most. 171(44.0 %) class teachers indicated that students who have two parents obey rules and only 33 (8.1 %) class teachers indicated that students who have one parents obeys rules. 113 (28.8 %) class teachers indicated that students who live with other relatives obey rules and 75 (19.1 %) class teachers indicated that students from the reconstituted families obey rules. Implying that students with one parent are less likely to obey rules.

Class teachers indicated that students from the reconstituted families were most uncooperative and unruly. 176(45.1%) class teachers indicated that students living in a reconstituted relationship were uncooperative and unruly while 27(6.9 %) class teachers indicated that students who had two parents were uncooperative and unruly. 110 (28.0%) class teachers indicated that students who live with other relatives were uncooperative and unruly and 78 (20.0 %) class teachers indicated that students who have one parent were uncooperative and unruly. The findings in Table 2 indicates that students living in reconstituted relationship, single parent or with other relatives were most uncooperative and unruly. These suggests that the presences of two biological parents in a relationship positively connects with the behaviour of a child.

The study further indicated that students living with other relatives influenced peers negatively most. 154(39.4%) class teachers indicated that students living with other relatives influenced

peers negatively while 54 (13.9 %) class teachers indicated that students who have two parents influenced peers negatively. 97(24.8%) class teachers indicated that students living in a reconstituted relationship also influenced peers negatively, and 86 (21.9 %) class teachers indicated that students who have one parents influenced peers negatively. This also indicates that students living with two parents had minimal negative influence on peers.

The study also indicated that a number of class teachers indicated that students who have one parent are likely to relate poorly with colleagues. 153(39.1%) class teachers indicated that students living in a reconstituted relationship are likely to relate poorly with colleagues and 56 (14.2 %) class teachers indicated that students living with other relatives relate poorly with colleagues. 111(28.5 %) class teachers indicated that those who have two parents relate poorly with colleagues and 71 (18.2 %) class teachers indicated that students who have one parent are likely to relate poorly with colleagues. This also indicates that students who have two parents whether biological or from a reconstituted relationship more likely relate poorly with colleagues. These can be linked to a child's mental confidence stemming from assistance and stable finances.

Descriptive Summary of Family Structure on Student Discipline

The study summarized the family structure on student discipline and recorded the findings in Table 3.

Table 3. Descriptive Summary of Family Structure on Student Discipline

Family structure	A. Two Parents	B. One Parent	C. Reconstituted Family	D. living with other relatives	Totals
Student's discipline	40	90	148	113	391
Percentage	10.1%	23.1%	37.9%	28.9%	100.0%

Data from Table 3 shows that an average of 391 class teachers participated in this section, out of these 113(28.9%) classes teachers felt that students who were living with other relatives were likely to have discipline problems. Another 148(37.9 %) class teachers felt that students living in a reconstituted relationships were likely to have discipline problems. 90 (23.1 %) class teachers felt that students who have one parent were likely to have discipline problems and 40(10.1 %) class teachers felt that students who have two parents were likely to have discipline problems. This indicates that students who lived

with other relatives had the most discipline problems in schools.

Correlation between the Family Structure and Students' Discipline

The study further sought to investigate the relationship between family structure and student discipline in public boarding secondary schools in Western region of Kenya. To do this, a Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was computed. The study findings are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Pearson Correlation of Family Structure and Students' Discipline

Family structure and discipline (Pearson Correlation)		0	A	B	C	D	
0	students' discipline	Sig.	1				
A	Two Parents	Sig	.852 .000	1			
B	One Parent	Sig	.485** .038	.127 .865	1		
C	living in a reconstituted relationship	Sig	.762** .000	.428** .046	.428** .482	1	
D	living with other relatives	Sig	.426** .038	.763** .000	.213 .256	.025 .785	1

Note: **. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

The findings of the study in Table 4 indicate that there was statistically significant ($p < .05$) positive correlation between family structure and students' discipline in public secondary schools in Western region of Kenya. All the four aspects of the family structure correlated with students' discipline in public secondary schools in Western region of Kenya.

The Pearson correlation index obtained on the first variable "Two parents" was $r = 0.852$, it is a strong positive correlation with $q < 0.0001$ which is less than $\alpha = 0.05$.

The second variable "One parent". ($r = 0.485$, $q = 0.038$) at $\alpha = 0.05$) Strongly positively

correlated with student discipline, the third variable "living in a reconstituted family relationship". ($r = 0.762$, $q < 0.001$) at $\alpha = 0.05$) strongly positively correlated with student discipline and the fourth variable "living with other relatives" also strongly correlated with student discipline. ($r = 0.426$, $q = 0.038$) at $\alpha = 0.05$).

The findings of the study in Table 4 shows that the correlations were between 0.426 to 0.852. Therefore, students' discipline was likely affected by family structure characteristics.

General Correlation between the Family Structure and Students' Discipline

To investigate whether there was any statistical relationship between the family structure and students' discipline, a Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was computed; with

overall scores from the four aspects of family structure. All the items were appropriately reversed so that the high scale represented a high level of family structure and students' discipline in public boarding secondary schools in Western region of Kenya. Table 5 shows the correlation analysis results.

Table 5. General Correlation between the Family Structure and Students' Discipline

	Pearson Correlation	students' discipline	Family structure
Student's discipline	Correlation	1	.723**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	n	391	391
Family structure	Correlation	.723**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	n	391	391

Note: **. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The findings in Table 5 of the study shows that there was statistically significant positive correlation ($r=0.723$, $n=391$, $p=0.023$) between the family structure and students' discipline.

Regression Analysis of the Family Structure and Students' Discipline

In order to estimate the level of influence of family structure on students' discipline, a coefficient of determination was computed using a regression analysis whose results were as shown in Table 6.

The model was of the form:

$$Y = \beta_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \epsilon \quad (1)$$

Where

Y = Students discipline

X_3 = Family structure

B_2 = Coefficient of variation

ϵ_1 = the error term.

Table 6. Model Summary (n=391)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.823 _a	.782	.624	.9658

Note: a. Predictors: (Constant), Family structure

The results for the model summary are as presented in Table 6 where R^2 (coefficient of multiple determinants) is shown. As the model depicts, the adjusted R^2 is 0.624, an indication that there is a relationship between family structure and students' discipline. This means

that a proportion of 62.4% of students' discipline can be explained by the family structure characteristics. The model significance was presented using the ANOVA test. The findings were summarized in Table 7.

Table 7. Summary of ANOVA tests (n=391)

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	63.256	1	201.352	78.365	.000 ^b
Residual	235.236	390	32.256		
Total	298.492	391			

Note: a. **Dependent Variable:** students’ discipline; b. **Predictors: (Constant),** family structure

The results in Table 7 indicated that the model was statistically significant. This was supported by an F statistic 78.365 and the reported p value

(0.000) which was less than 0.05 significance level.

Table 8. Regression Coefficients (n=391)

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	6.253	.6242		36.253	.000
Family structure	.521	.325	.429	8.235	.000

Note: a. **Dependent Variable:** students’ discipline; b. **Predictors: (Constant),** family structure

The results illustrated in Table 8 indicates that the t-test values for the family structure coefficient is significant (t= 8.235, p < 0.05). Based on the findings in Table 8, the study rejected the null hypothesis, Ho3, that,

“there is no statistically significant influence of family structure on student discipline in public boarding secondary schools in Western region of Kenya”.

Implying that the family structure significantly influenced students’ discipline in public secondary schools in Western region of Kenya. This can be attributed to the fact that children from two parent families were more likely to describe themselves as happy compared to step-families and single-parent families.

The findings in Table 8 are in tandem with those of Yang & Jiang (2023) who established that the behavioral and mental health of adolescents in single-parent or reconstituted families deserves more attention, and interventions should be actively conducted at both family and school level, to improve adolescent health.

Data in Table 8 indicate the unstandardized coefficient for the variable was 0.521 and the P-value is 0.000. The new model now becomes:

$$Y = 6.253 + 0.521X_3 + \epsilon$$

Where X₃= family structure .

Thus, implying that at a significance level of 0.05, family structure influences the students’ discipline by up to 43.5 %. The findings also indicate that the t-statistics (36.253) is higher than the t-critical, an indication that family structure significantly influences students’ discipline. It is evident from Table 8 that if the family structure improves by one standard deviation, then students’ discipline would improve by 0.521 standard deviation units.

Conclusion

According to the research findings, the study concludes that family structure significantly influences student discipline in public boarding secondary schools in Western region of Kenya.

Recommendation

In order to prevent indiscipline cases associated with discipline among learners, schools should plan for meetings to educate parents on the importance of providing personal effects to support their children at school.

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